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Torn Between Two Loves

What do you do when your heart is torn between the learners you teach and the child you must care for, between the life you know and the life you dream for them both?

As an ALS teacher, I've always poured my heart into my work. I've witnessed the struggles of my OSYA (Out-of-School Youth and Adults), individuals who wake up to realities I can't even begin to imagine. They don't have the luxury of a proper meal, let alone the stability of a safe and supportive home. But I do what I can. I send money for their snacks, and sometimes, if I have a little extra, I'll even buy their lunch or cover their fares to and from the Community Learning Center (CLC). I help because I know what it feels like to struggle.

But behind the smiles I try to put on for my OSYA, a single mom is battling the most challenging fight of all. I have an autistic daughter; my world. She needs me more than anyone. Her therapy, her medicines, her school tuition, her vitamins, her milk. These aren't just expenses. They are my daughter's lifeline, her chance at a future. Yet, no matter how hard I try, my salary is still not enough to cover everything. My heart aches as I watch her suffer, knowing that I can't give her everything she deserves.

There are days when I sit in silence, questioning everything. I wonder if I'm doing enough. I wonder if I'm giving my daughter the future she deserves, or if I'm just barely keeping my head above water. I wonder if I'm failing her.

And then, there's my OSYA, the individuals who depend on me. I see them struggling with things I cannot even fathom. Their pain is my pain; their hardships are my hardships. I want to be their lifeline, just as I want to be my daughter's. But lately, it feels like I'm being stretched too thin. I can't be in two places at once, and I can't give both my daughter and my OSYA everything they need.

That's when the thought crosses my mind: it's time to go abroad. There may be a chance for me to give my daughter the life she deserves. To give her the things she needs, without constantly worrying if we'll have enough. But that decision feels like a betrayal. The thought of leaving my OSYA behind, the very people who need me so desperately, breaks my heart in ways I can't describe.